

Institute of Discourse Perspective

2nd International Conference

Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics & Impact

The phenomenal speaker presents this research in 2nd International Conference Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics &, held on 25-27 April 2025 at Al-Razi Hall, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. The Conference Abstract is published on behalf of the decision of acceptance and approval of aforesaid Conference Organizing Committee.

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Citation:

Iram Shah, 2nd International Conference, Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics &, held in Al-Razi Hall, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. Vol. 12 (2025). p. 31-32.

Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information is available at the end of the article.

Conference Abstract

RESEARCH STUDY OF "SEERAT E SARWAR E AALAM IN TRADITIONAL WRITING STYLE OF SYED ABUL A'LA MAUDUDI

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Ethics approval and consent to participate: No ethical approval needed for this research work.

Consent for publication: Author is agreed to submit this abstract for publication in this research journal.

Availability of data and materials: The information and data collected and/ or incorporated in this study is included in this manuscript.

ABSTRACT

The ever-green subject of Seerah (Biography of the Holy Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) remained cause of interest to spoke and wrote by scholars throughout the history even since revelation of the Holy Quraan and will continue to be spoken and written in the future as well. Although, it is a vast subject to spoke and write and even can't be covered in a book but it always needed to write and speak more on it. Urdu Seerah writing is mostly indebted to Allama Shibli Nomani and his disciple Syed Sulaiman Nadvi. Most of the Urdu Seerah writers have copied and followed them in some extent. While, Maulana Syed Abul-Ala Maududi is unique among these Seerah writers. He only learned from them but put uniqueness to the "Sirat Sarwar-e-Alam" by his appealing and captivating writing through his knowledge, study, understanding, and intelligence, criticism, commentary, modern techniques of analysis, and the ancient style of criticism and interpretation. "Seerat Sarwar Alam" is not a formal written work by Maulana Syed Abul Ala Maududi, but rather a collection of Seerat material scattered in his commentary "Tafheem-ul-Quran" and other writings, which has been compiled by Maulana Naeem Siddiqui and Maulana Abdul Wakil Alvi from Maududi's vast and extensive collection of writings. However, he also contributed in proofreading, editing and final writing of the book. In this article, we are going to carryout overall research analysis of the book starting from the writer's introduction, his biography, family background along with educational and writing background. We will carry on deep research analysis of the

book starting from its contents' comprehensiveness, sources and references, content authentication, correlated historical events, trial of contents derived from or trial of Riwayah, writer's language and expression style and anything else concerned to the book.

Keywords: Syed Abul A'la Maududi, Seerah Writing, Seerah Books, Biography of Hazrat Muhammad (peace be upon him), Sources and References, Comprehensiveness of Content, Traditional Writing Style (Asloob), Trial of Content and Riwayah

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